

Synthesis and biological activity of some sulphonamoylazopyrazoles

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Some pyrazole derivatives of sulphonamides have been synthesised. Most of the compounds exhibit promising antibacterial activity.

In view of medicinal importance of pyrazoles¹ and sulphonamides², some pyrazole derivatives of sulphonamides have been synthesised with a view to enhance biological activity of sulphonamides.

Reaction of benzoyl acetone with different diazonium salts in presence of sodium acetate gave 2-(4'-sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-1-phenylbutane-1,3-diones (1a-g), which on cyclisation with 4-pyrimidine carboxylic acid hydrazide in presence of glacial acetic acid yielded 1-nicotinoyl-3-methyl-5-phenyl-4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)azopyrazoles (2a-g).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 833 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian spectrophotometer (270 MHz) using TMS as the internal standard. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel-G plates. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses. Sulphonamides which were not available in pure form were extracted from the commercially available sulpha drugs.

2-(4'-Sulphonamoyl)hydrazono-1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (1a) : to an ice-cold solution of sulphanilamide (0.02 mol) in a mixture of concentrated HCl (8 ml) and water (11 ml), cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (1.40 g) was added in portions in ice-cold condition. Diazonium salt so formed was filtered into already cooled (0°) solution mixture of sodium acetate (16 g) and benzoyl acetone (0.02 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), and the solution was stirred vigorously. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 124°; ν_{\max} 3260 (NH₂), 3060 (NH, H-bonded), 1660 (CO), 1510 (NH-N=C), 1115 (SO₂), 750 cm⁻¹ (phenyl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.0-8.0 (4H, ArH), 10.95 (1H, s, NH, H-bonded). Similarly, other compounds (yields 40-75%) of the series were prepared by coupling appropriate sulphonamides with benzoyl acetone : **1b**, m.p. 203°; **c**, 196°; **d**, 222°; **e**, 186°; **f**, 50°; **g**, 68°.

1-Nicotinoyl-3-methyl-5-phenyl-4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)-

azopyrazole (2a) : A mixture of **1a** (0.001 mol) and 4-pyrimidine carboxylic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) in acetic acid was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 h. The reaction

Scheme 1

Note

mixture was allowed to cool overnight and the separated solid was crystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. 218°; ν_{\max} 3325 (NH, H-bonded), 1520 (N=N), 1625 (C=N), 1140 (SO₂) and 750 cm⁻¹ (phenyl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.30 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.2 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.99–8.66 (9H, ArH). Similarly, other pyrazoles (yields 55–70%) were prepared : **2b**, m.p 185°; **c**, 195°; **d**, 218°; **e**, 212°; **f**, 82°; **g**, 205°.

Antibacterial activity : Antibacterial activity of compounds **2a-g** was tested *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus pyrogenus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Pseudomonas mongiferae* and *Vibris cholerae* by cup-plate technique³ in the concentration range 0.5–1.0 mg cm⁻³; sulphamethoxazole (zone of inhibition 25–30 mm against the

bacteria selected) was used as the control. Compounds **2b** and **2c** were found active (zone of inhibition 12–16 mm) against *P. mongiferae* and *S. aureus*, **2d** (10–14 mm) against *B. pumilus* and *S. aureus*, and **2e** (10–14 mm) against *V. cholerae* and *B. pumilus*. Rest of the compounds were inactive against all the organisms.

References

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